

R PACKAGES TO THE ANALYSIS OF RECURRENCE

A collection of R packages for studying recurrence plot as well as recurrence quantification analysis

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NONLINEARTSERIES (LAST UPDATE 2020)

Developed by Constantino A. G. Martínez

<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/nonlinearTseries/index.html>

CRQA: CROSS-RECURRENCE QUANTIFICATION ANALYSIS FOR CATEGORICAL AND CONTINUOUS TIME-SERIES (LAST UPDATE 2018)

Developed by Moreno I. Coco and Rick Dale

<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/nonlinearTseries/index.html>

RQA SOFTWARE (LAST UPDATE 2018)

Developed by Charles Webber Jr.

<http://cwebber.sites.luc.edu/>

FNONLINEAR: NONLINEAR AND CHAOTIC TIME SERIES MODELLING (LAST UPDATE 2017)

Developed by Diethelm Wuertz

<http://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/fNonlinear/index.html>

CASNET: AN R TOOLBOX FOR STUDYING COMPLEX ADAPTIVE SYSTEMS AND NETWORKS (LAST UPDATE 2020)

Developed by Fred Hasselmann

<https://github.com/FredHasselmann/casnet>

TSERIESCHAOS - FUNCTION RECURR (LAST UPDATE 2019)

Developed by Antonio, Fabio Di Narzo

<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/tseriesChaos/tseriesChaos.pdf>

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